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**Enhancing the resilience capacity of European mountain regions through
social innovation and knowledge sharing: selected implications from the
H2020 SIMRA project**

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Abstract

The rising demand of a growing world population for water, food, materials and energy puts increasing pressures on natural resources and ecosystems. Increased energy use has led to an increased demand for land and water. Environmental challenges, along with increased food and feed demands, will further enlarge pressures on land and water resources. Such pressures will be multiplied by the impacts of global changes, including of climate change, which are likely to further modify the availability and suitability of the resources and affect agricultural productivity and the well-being of communities living in marginalised rural areas, and particularly in the Mediterranean region, where the consequences of climate change (with a shortage of fresh water supply) are anticipated to be severe. Local level challenges (e.g. depopulation and ageing population) in such areas will likely intersect with global issues and require urgent solutions. The project ‘Social Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas’ (SIMRA), funded by the European Union’s (EU) Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, seeks to provide such solutions. The project is designed to fill the significant knowledge gap in understanding and enhancing social innovation in agriculture, forestry and rural development. This is seen as a way forward for marginalised rural areas across Europe and in the Mediterranean region, in particular, including non-EU Mediterranean; and the primary needs that social innovation via SIMRA is expected to deliver concern quality of life and human well-being.

1. Why social innovation is needed?

Social innovation (SI), as defined by the EU funded project SIMRA is *the reconfiguring of social practices in response to challenges associated with society, economy or environment based on novel ideas and values. These practices include the creation of new institutions, networks, and governance agreements, and seek to enhance societal outcomes, especially but not exclusively for disadvantaged groups, and recognizing the likelihood of trade-offs among competing interests and outcomes. While these practices may include diverse institutions, they necessarily include the voluntary engagement of civil society actors.* The principal implication of this definition is that SI is the means (the novel form of social action and practices) and not necessarily the sole arena or ends of the action, which could have economic, technological or environmental, as well as social outcomes. This definition

provides a starting point for the conceptualization and operationalization of SI in different contexts across Europe and the Mediterranean region.

In a period of global crisis, SI offers the potential to contribute to tackling contemporary societal challenges. At the global level, public institutions have identified social innovation as a key feature of global policies that aim to improve people's lives and stimulate development. Following the recent financial and economic crisis there is an urgent need to "shift to a new economic thinking" [...] "innovative models of growth and governance are needed to recreate trust among people [...] and to allow economic and social sustainability and transparency in decision making" (BEPA, 2011).

In rural areas, especially in Marginalised Rural Areas, social innovation can offer new solutions to tackling challenges that are created, in part, by the contemporary transformation into an increasingly global and knowledge-based economy (Nyseth and Aarsæther, 2005). People in such areas are increasing their capacity to innovate (OECD, 2007). Stimulating and enabling SI is a key component of emerging European policies, such as the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP; EC, 2011), as well as national and regional policies. However, there is a deficit in information about the implementation of SI (Knill and Lenschow, 2000). Although scholars have developed approaches for measuring the characteristics of SI processes, much remains to be done to link SIs to desired policy outcomes (Koontz and Thomas, 2006).

There is a requirement to identify effective incentives and mechanisms to stimulate SI. In turn, to use SI to aid in the development of Marginalised Rural Areas, there is a need to "deepen our knowledge about how SI works, grows and changes the way societies are driven", and to pay particular attention to local conditions and intermediating factors (BEPA, 2011). Such understanding should enable the design of means of supporting "regional SI systems" as ways of fostering SI as a core part of Rural Development policy (Dabson, 2011).

2. Towards social innovation through the SIMRA project

SIMRA is a research and innovation project supported by the EU (2016-2020). The overarching aim is to improve understanding of SI such that the knowledge and approaches developed jointly by scientists and stakeholders will increase the prospects of the successful implementation of SI on the ground. From the outset and throughout the project, SIMRA pursues a trans-disciplinary approach, involving stakeholders, likely end-users of the knowledge and tools developed, and researchers from a range of socio-economic and natural science backgrounds. A key aim is to encourage the engagement between stakeholders, the project partnership and across its wider network, assisted by effective and well-targeted means of knowledge exchange.

A structured, transdisciplinary approach to analysing and operationalizing of SI is being enabled by the development of systematic theoretical and operational frameworks. These frameworks are supporting the identification of actual and potential roles of SI in realising territorial capital. They will be used to explain why regions with similar initial conditions for SI have diverging pathways for evolution, and understanding the barriers and factors underpinning success, and the formulation of lessons learned from observing SI in action.

A structured approach to the selection of case studies is enabled by categorising SIs in rural areas, recording social needs, priorities, and types of social relationships and collaborations. These SIs and their impacts are being evaluated using a toolbox of methods developed for the purpose. They will complement existing European frameworks, such as the Common Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (CMEF), and enable consideration of the nature and

significance of economic, sociological, environmental, governance and institutional components of territorial capital.

The evaluation of factors influencing the success of SI will recognise the heterogeneity of regions in terms of their biophysical conditions, socio-economic development, social capital, governance and institutional settings. This evaluation will improve the understanding of the development of SIs, with particular attention paid to the emergence or design of new governance mechanisms. The aim is to equip policy makers, end-users and communities with information and tools that support the creation of conditions conducive to SI options in challenged regions. In particular, this will seek to clarify and promote the role of SI in developing more sustainable water and land resource management and agro-food and forestry systems, and shaping trajectories of sustainable development. It is anticipated that this will engender improvements in territorial capital and regional governance, and a more integrated approach to rural development.

Community perspectives on local approaches to sustainable natural resource management are being explored and innovative tools being tested. Figure 1 shows an example of engaging communities which are local and non-local to a region to identify any differences and inform thinking about governance (i.e. who has rights to making decisions about water and land management in catchments). A Virtual Landscape Theatre provides a forum for discussion about alternative futures (Wang et al., 2015), in this case identifying opportunities for local amenities based on a fishing facility, and means of mitigating risks to water quality due to agricultural inputs and of development on flood plains.

Figure 1. Eliciting community perspectives on opportunities and risks for improving social and natural resource resilience in a water catchment in north-east Scotland.

The SIMRA work is ongoing in the following main directions: i) development of frameworks for the categorization, understanding, and operationalizing SI in different settings and across spatial scales; ii) identification and understanding of reasons for diverging paths of SI development in regions with similar conditions; iii) advancement of an integrated set of methods for evaluating SI, and its impacts, in rural areas across Europe and the Mediterranean region; iv) evaluation of success factors for SIs, co-constructed by academic and practitioner communities for selected case studies; v) generation of new and improved knowledge of SI to be communicated to policy, practice and academia; and, vi) on collaborative learning, creating networking opportunities which lead to innovative actions (IAs).

These objectives are being achieved through advancing the state-of-the-art in understanding SI. SIMRA blends diverse theoretical positions into a coherent explanation of SI and its relationships to governance mechanisms, social needs, drivers and motivations, and empirical research in a set of case studies.

3. The SIMRA team

The consortium comprises 26 partners in 15 countries from across the EU and the wider Mediterranean area, and associated international networks. It consists of 10 public bodies (8 universities and 2 research institutes), 8 not for profit organizations, 5 SMEs, NGOs and networks, and 3 international organisations (SIMRA, 2016). Representatives from other countries, including North Africa and Eastern Europe participate as supporters of SIMRA, coming from the South and South-Eastern European Mountain Network, the Carpathian Network of ‘Science for the Carpathians’, International Union of Forest Research Organizations, FLEG II, Earth System Governance, Ecosystem Services Community Scotland, and others. Although Ukraine, for example, is not represented as a partner country, its experts contribute to activities of the SI Think Tank of SIMRA. At the proposal stage SIMRA received support from 31 agencies, science and membership organizations to provide two-way pathways for sharing knowledge and creating impact across the regions of interest.

SIMRA examines what characterises SI in areas as varied as north-west Europe and Scandinavia, the Mediterranean and North Africa region, Alpine, Central and Eastern Europe, and regions of Member States out-with the European area (e.g. Guadeloupe, France). The project team collaborates with those initiating or benefiting from SI to learn about end-user motivations, and experiences of supporting SI or the barriers encountered. The research consortium is characterised by its trans-disciplinary composition of research teams, practitioners, NGOs, networks, and organisations with remits for the development of policy, from local to global. As a consequence, project expertise comprises scientific understanding, education, knowledge exchange and dissemination, business, market and entrepreneurship proficiency, and policy evaluation and implementation.

4. Defining social innovation

Research into SI has spanned disciplines and domains of application. To date (Westley, 2016), work has focused on research areas: social entrepreneurship and social enterprise; innovation processes; institutional entrepreneurship; social-technical transitions and multi-scale interactions; resilience and social-ecological transformations; and social economy. Such variety of applications is a reflection of the diversity of theoretical and operational approaches to SI. Some definitions emphasize the end results of social innovation, i.e. “answer to social problems” (OECD, 2012), or the transformative processes it generates (MacCallum et al., 2016) with the main rationale of a social innovation to:

- Build capacity to create and implement new ideas to deliver value (BEPA, 2011);
- Create new outcomes, i.e. ideas, products, services, models, and new processes and changes that should, ideally, meet individual and societal needs;
- Develop new institutional environments and arrangements, actor relationships and interactions (e.g. attitudes, collaborations, values, behaviours, skills, practices and learning processes), and fields of activity (e.g. social entrepreneurship and enterprise);
- Expand the potential for upscaling and diffusion of SI, as it begins with ideas, develops into prototypes and pilots, can become more stable and potentially up-scale and may eventually create a systemic change.

Social innovation aims at improving the quality of life and well-being through creating new responses to pressing social demands and responding to social demands that are traditionally not addressed by existing institutions. SI manifests itself in new social relationships and

collaborations. It advances social capital and enables new governance mechanisms, based on new social networks. SI and enhanced governance are considered crucial for transition towards sustainable development and enhancing smart and inclusive growth. Social innovation and connected new governance mechanisms can be macro or micro, structural or local, vertical or horizontal, introduced by entrepreneurs or solidarity, by institutional changes or/and policy reforms (Nussbaumer and Moulaert, 2007). However, whatever their nature, context or scale; they strengthen actor's abilities to respond to societal challenges, such as poverty, food security, climate change etc. including those related to the demand and supply of water resources (Lehtonen, 2004).

5. Characterising marginalised rural areas

SIMRA is focusing on SI in rural areas which are both marginal and in which people are marginalized. These are referred to as Marginalised Rural Areas (MRAs). To understand the characteristics of such areas, a review has been undertaken of literature and associated relevant definitions adopted by international agencies. Many definitions have been published or adopted for 'rural'. Van Eupen et al. (2012: 473) state that "it is not feasible to agree to a single definition for the term" given the diversity of situations and scientific perspectives. The simplest dichotomy is that what is not urban is rural, or 'the countryside'; although there should be recognition of the reality of an urban-rural continua, with urban areas and rural hinterlands overlapping and interlinking (Courtney et al., 2009).

Several definitions are used within EU Member States, a list of overviews of which is available from the European Parliamentary Research Service <https://epthinktank.eu/2012/11/28/4589/>. Criteria were considered to identify thresholds dividing urban from rural, using population size, density, and context (Gessert et al., 2015). The interpretation of MRA comprises identifying and characterising those definable as rural and those of marginalised people in rural areas. Underlying the approach is the aim to represent factors influencing, stimulating or inhibiting SI in MRAs:

- Rural areas (EC / population density), assumed to contain identifiable communities.
- Marginal areas in terms of physical geography (i.e. spatial marginality, Gurung and Kollmair, 2005): a) mountainous b) islands; c) low agricultural potential due to aridity (Strijker, 2005), limiting primary sector dominance (Bock, 2016).
- Marginal areas in terms of very limited access to infrastructure (e.g. internet access as a surrogate); marginalised populations, cf. societal marginality (Gurung and Kollmair, 2005): inhabitants with (very) low incomes (as measured by GDP).

Based on reviewing relevant literature and use of existing data, SIMRA incorporated biophysical and socio-economic knowledge and information to create a database created for the spatial representation of characteristics of MRAs, starting with administrative areas for the EU and South and South-Eastern Mediterranean EU and the Mediterranean region. The comprehensive data were combined to produce a consistent dataset of rural and intermediate rural areas for the region; mountainous areas and areas limited for agricultural productivity (Strijker, 2005, largely due to the shortage of fresh water and drought). Socio-economic data being compiled represent GDP, accessibility by types of road networks, and data on internet access and risks of poverty or social exclusion.

The compiled database will be developed to provide a basis for categorising examples of SIs across Europe and the wider Mediterranean region. The output will provide background information for the interpretation of how different types of SIs have evolved in response to environmental and socio-economic conditions of MRAs. These data will be used to evaluate

the impacts of SI across case study areas in agriculture, forestry and rural development, and the importance of the water based sector.

6. Selected directions of future development

An innovative, integrated set of methods is in preparation for the evaluation of the characteristics and impacts of SI, and their relationship with the economic, social, environmental, institutional and governance requirements of territorial capital in rural areas. This set will be used to collect empirical evidence of SI and its impacts in selected case studies across Europe and the Mediterranean region with examples such as community-based micro-hydro renewable energy, community food production.

The evaluation will provide a thorough consideration of the components of territorial capital that can foster and mainstream rural development. The current political frameworks will be analysed to assess the extent to which they support SI in MRAs at international and national levels. The aim is to understand the implications of project findings for policy making and practice communities.

A range of conditions will be considered in relation to financing SI covering issues such as regulations, public-private partnerships, new business opportunities and new markets, and the roles of intermediaries, knowledge brokers and entrepreneurs. Through exploring opportunities SIMRA will encourage stakeholder engagement and the mobilisation of private funds to make SI practical.

7. A trans-disciplinary approach and knowledge flow

SIMRA explores SIs through the entire cycle (Young Foundation, 2012) of the SI spiral model: from ideas, to prototyping and piloting, to implementation, and to upscaling; or, from ideas to production/market (e.g. new entrepreneur opportunities) and to innovative policy and governance mechanisms within each scale and across the scales. The aim is to enhance SIs that are both driven by end-users (or agent-based factors, which can be private, public, mixed or based on partnerships) and relevant to them. Attention is paid to new social networks/partnerships. The trans-disciplinary science of SIMRA addresses the complexity and causalities of SI actions, linking abstract knowledge through the SI processes towards a range of experience-based competencies and skills, i.e. target knowledge (a set of SIMRA's SI outputs making impacts in MRAs), illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 2. Systems model of knowledge flow in SIMRA (Source: SIMRA Project Document, 2016, produced for the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 677622).

The multi-actor driven approach of SIMRA targets case studies (CS) where scientists ‘set the scene’ on existing scientific knowledge, and stakeholders provide input to developing trans-disciplinary knowledge and co-constructing investigative approaches. The innovative knowledge and approaches of SIMRA developed jointly in its science and stakeholder labs flow throughout the project to support the build-up and promotion of SIs on the ground.

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- Facebook: www.facebook.com/SIMRAeu/
- Twitter: https://twitter.com/simra_eu/status/753903906443370496
- Scoop it!: www.scoop.it/u/simra-1
- Research Gate: www.researchgate.net/project/SIMRA-Social-Innovation-in-Marginalised-Rural-Areas
- LinkedIn: www.linkedin.com/groups/8546624/8546624-6159676893563015168

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